

Rac-4g

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-177-rac-re-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	92	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	xt 2 177 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	264.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 264.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/3/2021 9:48:46 PM CST		
Date Processed:	11/3/2021 10:05:08 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.544	2702276	50.40	227890
2	11.071	2659861	49.60	115797

Asy-4g

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-177-rac-20%-IG	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	70	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 178
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	264.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 264.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	11/3/2021 9:21:48 PM CST		
Date Processed:	11/3/2021 10:07:32 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	6.537	6036127	96.96	524631
2	11.054	189374	3.04	7855